

COCOREADO H2020 PROJECT

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

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Introduction

This Toolkit is a collection of practical tools, useful tips, and sources of inspiration to support innovation towards re-connecting consumers and producers, to rebalance farmers' position in Food Supply Chains.

The materials found in the Toolkit have been brought together and validated within the HORIZON 2020 project COCOREADO, designed to rebalance the position of the farmer as an individual actor, a key player in innovative food supply chains, and a supplier for public procurement. The project has involved both academic and farming community partners across Europe, recognising regional differences and barriers (in terms of replicability of good practices) and regional opportunities (in terms of solutions).

A substantial part of the project has been building and maintaining the COCOREADO Ambassador Network of 40 young people passionate about food and agriculture, who are willing to facilitate sustainable changes in food systems. You can learn more about the [COCOREADO ambassadors community here](#).

The material you find in the Toolkit has been validated with these ambassadors over a two-year period, in face-to-face trainings and beyond.

By clicking on the links that you find within the Toolkit you can access other related sources and materials.

Chapters

[The Toolkit consists of five chapters:](#)

DEVELOPING NETWORKS

This chapter aims to define the most important elements to be considered when designing and developing a network to facilitate change within food systems. Practical steps and experiences from developing the COCOREADO Ambassador Network are offered as an example for developing a long-term network of food system innovators.

GETTING INSPIRED FROM EXAMPLES

This chapter focuses on different ways that good practices can be identified and studied, and ways that their lessons can be applied to improve food systems in different contexts and regions.

COMMUNICATING CHANGE

This chapter outlines key elements for developing effective communication, provides practical communication tips, and gives in-depth insights on communication through selected contemporary channels, such as social media, video, and podcasts.

ENGAGING WITH POLICY

This chapter explores ways that the agenda setting phase can be influenced from a bottom-up perspective. Here you will find information on how to:

- Establish policy-oriented communication;
- Produce a policy brief;
- Prepare a policy workshop;
- Address and engage with a local urban food policy.

DEVELOPING AN IDEA INTO BUSINESS

In this chapter, the tools used in the COCOREADO ambassador training programme, with the aim of developing seed initiatives, are presented. It covers everything from fleshing out a preliminary idea to an initial definition of the business model.

You can either get acquainted with the chapters in the order they have been presented, or easily jump to the sections that interest you most.

When getting familiar with the material, you may encounter the following abbreviations:

CAP Common Agricultural Policy

COCOREADO Connecting consumers and producers to rebalance farmers' position

CSA Community supported agriculture

EU European Union

FAO Food and Agriculture Organisation

LFS Local food system

NGO Non-governmental organisation

NOFA Novel and fair food system good practice

NPO Non-profit organisation

OECD Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

SFSC Short food supply chain

UFS Urban food strategy

Organisations involved

The following organisations have contributed to the development of the Food System Innovator toolkit:

BSC
Nodibinajums Baltic
Studies Centre

CEJA
European Council of
Young Farmers

CONSULAI
Consultoria
Agroindustrial LDA

INI
Iniciativas
Innovadoras SAL

EV ILVO
Flanders Research
Institute for Agricultural
and Fisheries Research

INTIA
Institute for Agri-food
Technology and
Infrastructures of Navarre

IPS
Institute of Philosophy
and Sociology

JSI
Jozef Stefan Institute

KU LEUVEN
University of Leuven

LUT
Lappeenrannana-Lahden
Teknillinen Yliopisto LUT

MIJARC
Jozef Stefan Institute

RYEUROPE
Rural Youth Europe EV

UCPH
University of Copenhagen

We hope this material offers you some inspiration and new ideas!

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